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Mathematical Modeling And Solution Of Deformed Cylindrical Compressible Blatz-Ko Material Under Torsional Effects Using Shooting Method

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ABSTRACT

This study considered the finite deformation of a compressible hyperelastic cylindrical material under torsional impacts. A mathematical model was developed considering the Blatz-Ko strain energy function which described the material's nonlinear elastic behaviour. The governing equations are derived and solved to obtain the displacement distributions. A numerical simulation is conducted using Wolfram Mathematica (version 12), and the system of nonlinear second-order differential equation is solved using shooting method. The study shows that material compressibility and internal pressure significantly influence deformation displacement. Materials with lower material constant (η) deform more, while those with higher η exhibit resistance to compression but may experience peak deformation at the boundary layers.

Keywords: Torsion, Compressible, Hyper-elastic, Wolfram, Pressure, Deformation, Material and Displacement.

INTRODUCTION

In solid mechanics, deformation is the process by which a material body changes size or shape in response to outside forces or environmental conditions like electromagnetic fields, pressure, or temperature. Deformation can be either plastic (permanent) or elastic (reversible), depending on the strength and type of applied pressures. When the applied forces are removed, materials revert to their initial configuration in the setting of elastic deformation, which is of special importance in this study. In engineering applications, mathematical modelling of deformation aids in predicting how materials would behave under various loading scenarios, directing design and safety evaluations.

In this work, a cylindrical body composed of a Blatz-Ko material which is a kind of compressible material that resembles rubber subject to torsional effects is mathematically modelled and solved. Rotational shear deformations brought about by torsion result in internal tensions and configurational changes in the material. The resulting boundary value problem governing the deformation is solved numerically using the shooting method.

The fundamental ideas of deformation, compressible materials, Blatz-Ko materials, torsional effects, and the shot method are explained in detail in this introduction, which serves as the theoretical basis for the ensuing modeling and analysis.

The term "deformation" describes how the application of forces can change a material body's dimensions or shape. Measures like stress (internal resistance to deformation) and strain (relative movement of particles within the material) are used to quantify it.

A deformation gradient tensor, F , which translates the initial (reference) configuration of material points to their present configuration, describes how a body deforms in continuum mechanics. One way to describe the type of deformation is by:

Elastic Deformation: A transient deformation that goes away when the applied stress is removed.

Plastic Deformation: Deformation that persists long after the stimulus has been eliminated. Time-dependent deformation that demonstrates both elastic and viscous characteristics is known as visco-elastic deformation.

Material-specific constitutive models govern the relationship between stress and strain in nonlinear elasticity, particularly under massive deformations. These models, which successfully anticipate material response under complicated loading scenarios like torsion, express stress as a function of strain and material parameters.

Rubber-like materials can withstand high strains and yet regain their original shape, which is one of their distinctive mechanical behaviour under huge deformations. A particular constitutive model designed to explain the behaviour of compressible rubber materials was the Blatz-Ko material model, which was first presented in the 1960s.

The strain energy density function, W , is determined by the Blatz-Ko model, which assumes that the material is compressible and isotropic.

Hyperelastic materials have gained considerable attention due to their applications in engineering, biomechanics, and material science. Hyperelastic materials are characterized by their ability to deform for large amounts and also return to their original shape once the load is removed. Hyperelastic materials play an important role in many applications ranging from soft robotics, biomedical implants, to structural engineering. Among the several models used to describe hyperelasticity, the Blatz-Ko model has worked well in describing compressible nonlinear elastic materials (Musenich, Strozzi, Avalle, & Libonati, 2025). Cylindrical members of compressible hyperelastic material are prone to deformation when subjected to loads from external forces like pressure, torsion, and shearing stresses (Egbuhuzor & Augustine, 2023). Performance under such conditions guides the way such material is designed with the best mechanical properties for them to have a longer lifespan. The deformation of cylindrical materials is regulated by the deformation gradient tensor that considers a material's deformation in relation to its initial shape.

Hyperelastic materials, having the ability to experience huge deformation and return to their initial form, have prominent application in the fields of biomechanics, soft robotics, and materials engineering.

The paper by Khalaj-Hedayati and Khodakarami (2019) presents a simple method for analyzing arbitrary domain shapes using a single element based on the Decoupled Scaled Boundary Finite Element Method (DSBFEM). The proposed element, built on the boundary finite element method, effectively models curved and sharp boundaries with high accuracy. While the shape and mapping functions are similar to those in DSBFEM, a key improvement is the relocation of the locating center origin (LCO) from the corners to the geometric center of the domain. This adjustment enhances the formulation and performance of the method. A major advantage of the proposed technique is its ability to solve displacement fields by directly solving differential equations, leading to more accurate results. Numerical tests and benchmark examples demonstrate the method's high accuracy, reliability, low computational cost, and its effectiveness in handling complex boundary shapes.

Torsion stresses usually cause considerable deformation in the cylindrical bodies of blood veins and elastomeric tubes. Though incompressible hyper-elastic materials such as rubbers have well-established solutions for finite torsion (Rivlin, 1997), there are new challenges with compressible ones. Compressibility is the measure of a material's ability to undergo a change in volume when subjected to pressure or other mechanical forces. In contrast to incompressible materials, which maintain a constant volume under deformation (i.e., $J=1$), **compressible materials** permit volumetric strains, where $J \neq 1$

The mechanical behavior of compressible materials is influenced by two key aspects:

- **Shear Deformation:** Changes in shape without volume change.
- **Volumetric Deformation:** Changes in volume without necessarily altering shape.

In modeling compressible materials, it is essential to maintain a proper equilibrium between shear and volumetric energy contributions. Compressibility influences the distribution of stress and the patterns of deformation, particularly when subjected to complex loads like torsion. Blatz-Ko materials are compressible and thus need mathematical models that consider alterations in both shape and volume, which renders the modeling process more intricate yet more accurate for specific applications.

The importance of compressibility is especially pronounced in torsional deformation, as both shearing and radial and axial impacts affect the material's response.

Torsion is the twisting of a structural element around its long axis as a result of applied torque. Torsional deformation creates shear stresses that change with the radial position in the cylinder absent at the axis and highest at the outer surface.

In an ideal cylindrical object, classical torsion theory suggests that cross-sections maintain their flat shape and rotate in relation to one another without distortion. Nevertheless, with significant deformations and for compressible substances such as Blatz-Ko materials, the torsional behavior turns nonlinear, and warping could take place. From a mathematical perspective, torsion can be represented through a displacement field that takes the following form: $\theta = \theta(r, z)$

Where;

θ represents the angle of rotation,

r denotes the radial coordinate, and

z represents the axial coordinate.

Key factors to take into account when modeling torsional effects consist of:

Shear Stress Distribution: Varied throughout the cross-section.

Geometric Nonlinearity: Important during extensive deformations.

Material Nonlinearity: Resulting from the constitutive properties of Blatz-Ko materials.

Boundary value problems (BVPs) often occur in modeling material deformation, particularly when the solution needs to meet criteria at two or more boundaries. Analytical solutions for nonlinear boundary value problems are frequently unfeasible, requiring the application of numerical techniques.

The shooting method is an effective approach for addressing BVPs by converting them into initial value problems (IVPs). The approach includes:

Estimating the unspecified initial conditions.

Addressing the resultant IVP with conventional ODE solvers (e.g., Runge-Kutta techniques).

Refining the initial estimate repeatedly until the solution meets the boundary conditions.

The stages involved in the shooting method generally consist of:

Establishing a preliminary estimate for unknown derivatives or values.

Combining the differential equations throughout the domain.

Calculating the disparity between the calculated and intended boundary conditions.

Adjusting the initial estimate through techniques such as Newton-Raphson iteration.

In the scope of this study, the deformation equations for the torsion of a Blatz-Ko cylindrical material result in a series of nonlinear differential equations subject to boundary conditions at various radii (inner and outer surfaces). The shooting technique allows for the efficient and precise solving of these equations accurately.

The selection of the shooting technique is driven by:

Its capacity to manage extremely nonlinear issues.

Its simple execution in comparison to other BVP solvers such as finite difference or finite element approaches.

Its alignment with adaptive step-size management in ODE solvers enhances computational efficiency.

In this study, the cylinder composed of Blatz-Ko material undergoes torsion, and the resulting intricate deformation is analyzed using mathematical modeling.

Investigating cylindrical structures subjected to torsion is a classical problem in continuum mechanics with broad applications in engineering disciplines. A particularly intriguing area of study involves the behavior of cylindrical bodies composed of hyperelastic materials, such as the Blatz-Ko constitutive model, when subjected to torsional loads (Benasciutti et al., 2011). The Blatz-Ko material model is renowned for its ability to accurately represent the mechanical response of compressible rubber-like solids under large deformations. When dealing with cylindrical geometries under torsion, the governing equations can sometimes be simplified to a one-dimensional form, dependent on the radial and axial coordinates, thereby reducing the computational complexity (Benasciutti et al., 2011). The Blatz-Ko material model is renowned for its ability to accurately represent the mechanical response of compressible rubber-like solids under large deformations. When dealing with cylindrical geometries under torsion, the governing equations can sometimes be simplified to a one-dimensional form, dependent on the radial and axial coordinates, thereby reducing the computational complexity (Benasciutti et al., 2011). However, the inherent nonlinearity of the material model and the geometric complexity introduced by torsion often necessitate the use of numerical methods, such as the shooting method, to obtain accurate solutions (Maurin & Spadoni, 2016).

The lack of isochoric constraints complicates their deformation behavior and necessitates special strain-energy functions for model representation accurately (Polignone and Horgan, 1991; Kirkinis and Ogden, 2002). Compressive torsion has been studied theoretically and experimentally to understand the behavior of such materials. Shrivastava and Canova(1982) and Valiollahi et al(2019) presented information on torque required for sustaining deformation, whereas Currie and Hayes (1981) presented constitutive equations for pure torsion. The study will build on these works by considering the Blatz-Ko material's torsional behavior when the material is compressible, using the Runge-Kutta approach in seeking numerical solutions.

Chibueze and Julius (2021) considered isotropic, incompressible hollow cylindrical structure undergoing pure azimuthal shear deformation. They concentrated on the development of the constitutive equation for an initially stressed material that lacks any inherent material symmetry. Kassianidis et al(2008) examined the problem of azimuthal shear of a cylinder under finite deformation, a general strain energy function was used and a closed form solution was obtained for a reinforced Neo Hookean material which was used to determine the region of strong ellipticity in terms of the shear strain and the angle. Bechir et al(2006) studied the behaviour of isotropic and incompressible vulcanized natural rubbers and that of quasi-incompressible carbon black filled vulcanized natural rubbers considering both theoretically and experimentally obtained solutions by generalizing the neo-Hookean model and derived an original form of the strain energy density function. Jiang and Ogden (2000) provided some new solutions for the axial shear of a circular cylindrical tube of compressible isotropic elastic material and discussed explicit solution for several forms of the strain energy function, analyzing the plain strain characterized of finite torsion shear cylinder of a compressible elastic material. In his 1996 dissertation, *Finite Deformations of a Generalized Blatz-Ko Material*, Wang investigates the finite deformations of a class of compressible, isotropic elastic materials characterized by a two-parameter strain energy function, which generalizes the Blatz-Ko model for foam rubbers. Using the semi-inverse method, Wang derives closed-form solutions

for various non-homogeneous deformations (such as the straightening of a sector, bending of blocks, eversion, and expansions of cylindrical and spherical shells) and solves related boundary value problems analytically and numerically. He identifies cases where solutions do not exist or are non-unique and addresses these based on physical reasoning. Homogeneous deformations are also explored, showing that materials with one parameter greater than or equal to two behave similarly to Blatz-Ko foam rubbers but become stiffer as the parameter increases. Wang also reformulates conditions for strong ellipticity to study instability, finding that certain boundary value problem solutions lose stability at critical load values. Motaghian et al. (2023) presents an eigenstrain analysis for a specific class of compressible, isotropic nonlinear elastic solids, known as Blatz–Ko materials. The objective is to investigate the deformations and stress fields generated by eigenstrain distributions in three structures made of Blatz–Ko materials: (1) a cylindrical wedge with axisymmetric cylindrical eigenstrains, (2) a cylindrical bar with axisymmetric torsional and cylindrical eigenstrains, and (3) a spherical ball with a spherically symmetric eigenstrain distribution. For each case, the deformation form is initially assumed to embed the material manifold (with Riemannian geometry) into Euclidean space, after which the governing equilibrium equations are derived and solved. The study focuses particularly on structures containing an inclusion with uniform eigenstrain, examining conditions under which stresses become uniform, hydrostatic, or singular (at the cylinder axis or sphere center). To support the theoretical findings, numerical examples are provided for each problem, enhancing understanding of the analysis. Bechir et al. (2023) investigate the **extension and inflation of a thick cylindrical tube** made from **compressible isotropic Mooney–Rivlin (MR) materials**, a model derived from the generalized Blatz–Ko model by fixing the Poisson’s ratio. They transform the balance equations into **second-order nonlinear ordinary differential equations (ODEs)** and solve them numerically to compute the **Cauchy stresses** across the tube’s deformed thickness. In the case of a **thin-walled tube or membrane**, the calibration of MR material constants is formulated as an **inverse problem**. Finite element (FE) simulations are also employed to analyze the stress distribution. The study suggests that experimental data from such extension-inflation tests can be effectively used to **identify and validate MR models for compressible isotropic soft gels and elastomers**.

This work intends to bridge this gap by numerically analyzing the torsional behavior of compressible Blatz-Ko materials using the Wolfram Mathematica to perform a numerical simulation by applying NDSolve using shooting method to solve the system of differential equations.

MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

Consider the cylindrical deformation of a cylinder where the deformation takes the point with the cylindrical coordinates (r, θ, z) in the reference configuration to the coordinates (R, ϕ, Z) .

Let e_R represent a unit vector normal to the cylinder e_ϕ represent a unit vector circumferential to the cylinder chosen to make $\{e_R, e_\phi, e_Z\}$ a right-handed triad. e_Z is parallel to the k vector.

The triad of vectors $\{e_R, e_\phi, e_Z\}$ is an orthonormal basis. Consequently, tensors can be represented as components in this basis. In particular, a general second order tensor \mathbf{S} can be represented as a 3x3 matrix given as

$$\bar{\mathbf{S}} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{RR} & S_{R\phi} & S_{RZ} \\ S_{\phi R} & S_{\phi\phi} & S_{\phi Z} \\ S_{ZR} & S_{Z\phi} & S_{ZZ} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The Deformation Gradient Tensor: Let us define the gradient operator, which, in cylindrical-polar coordinates, has the representation

$$\nabla = e_R \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{e_\phi}{R} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} + e_Z \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \tag{2}$$

In addition, the nonzero derivatives of the basis vectors are

$$\nabla = \frac{\partial e_R}{\partial r} = e_\phi \quad \frac{\partial e_\phi}{\partial \theta} = -e_R \tag{3}$$

Then the deformation gradient tensor F can be represented as a dyadic product of the tensor S with the gradient operator as

$$\bar{F} = \bar{S} \otimes \nabla = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial S_R}{\partial r} & \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial S_R}{\partial \theta} & \frac{\partial S_R}{\partial z} \\ S_R \frac{\partial S_\phi}{\partial r} & \frac{R}{r} \frac{\partial S_\phi}{\partial \theta} & S_R \frac{\partial S_\phi}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial S_Z}{\partial r} & \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial S_Z}{\partial \theta} & \frac{\partial S_Z}{\partial z} \end{bmatrix} \tag{4}$$

Deformation Measures: Let \mathbf{B} represent the Left Cauchy-Green deformation tensor, then,

$$\bar{B} = \bar{F} \cdot \bar{F}^T \Rightarrow \bar{B} = F_{ik} F_{jk} ; \quad J = \det(\bar{F})$$

The invariants of \mathbf{B} are given as:

$$I_1 = \text{trace } \bar{B} = \sum_{k=1}^3 B_{kk} \tag{5}$$

$$I_2 = \frac{1}{2} (I_1^2 - \text{trace } \bar{B}^2) \tag{6}$$

$$I_3 = \det(\bar{B}) = J^2 \tag{7}$$

Let e_1, e_2 and e_3 denote the three eigenvalues of \mathbf{B} . The principal stretches are given as

$$\lambda_1 = \sqrt{e_1}, \quad \lambda_2 = \sqrt{e_2}, \quad \lambda_3 = \sqrt{e_3}$$

Stress Measures

Usually stress-strain laws are given as equations relating Cauchy stress, ('true' stress) σ_{ij} to left Cauchy-Green deformation tensor. The Cauchy ("true") stress represents the force per unit deformed area in the solid and is defined by

$$n_i \sigma_{ij} = \lim_{dA \rightarrow 0} \frac{dP_j^{(n)}}{dA} \tag{8}$$

Note that, by definition, if the solid is subjected to some history of strain, the rate of change of the strain energy density $W(F)$ must equal the rate of mechanical work done on the material per unit reference volume. Equivalently, W only depends on F through its principal stretches $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ (the square roots of the principal values of B).

The ratio of the deformed configuration to the undeformed configuration is called a stretch, i.e.,

$$\text{Stretch}(\lambda_1) = \frac{|dR|}{|dr|}, \quad \text{Stretch in the radial direction}$$

$$\text{Stretch}(\lambda_2) = \frac{|d\phi|}{|d\theta|}, \quad \text{Stretch in the angular direction}$$

$$\text{Stretch}(\lambda_3) = \frac{|dZ|}{|dz|}, \quad \text{Stretch in the azimuthal direction}$$

With a slight abuse of notation, we write $W = W(I_1, I_2, I_3)$.

To compute the explicit form of the Cauchy stress tensor for a compressible material in terms of the invariants and their derivatives we use

$$\frac{\partial I_1}{\partial \bar{F}} = 2\bar{F}^T, \quad \frac{\partial I_2}{\partial \bar{F}} = 2I_1\bar{F}^T - 2\bar{F}^T\bar{B}, \quad \frac{\partial I_3}{\partial \bar{F}} = 2I_3\bar{F}^{-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{\sigma} = \omega_0 I + \omega_1 \bar{B} + \omega_2 \bar{B}^2,$$

Where the constants ω_i depend on the invariants and are given explicitly by

$$\omega_0 = 2J \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_3} - p, \quad \omega_1 = 2J^{-1} \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_1} + 2J^{-1} \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_2} I_1, \quad \omega_2 = -2J^{-1} \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_2}.$$

where p is the hydrostatic pressure and we choose $p = 0$ for compressible materials.

Development of Model Equation for the Finite Deformation of a Cylindrical Compressible Hyperelastic Material

Let us consider the torsional finite deformation of an elastic solid circular cylinder of radius a due to applied twisting moments at its ends,

$$\begin{aligned} R &= \eta R(r) & 0 < r \leq a \\ \phi &= \theta + \tau z & 0 < \theta \leq 2\pi \\ Z &= z & 0 < z \leq L \end{aligned}$$

where (r, θ, z) and (R, ϕ, Z) are the cylindrical coordinates in the reference and in the current configurations, respectively, $dR/dr < 0$, and the constant $\tau > 0$ is the twist per unit undeformed length. η is a positive constant which accounts for initial compressibility. Let us consider the strain energy function in terms of the first three principal invariants of \mathbf{B} , $W = W(I_1, I_2, I_3)$. The deformation gradient tensor \mathbf{F} is given by

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}} = \begin{bmatrix} \eta R' & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{R}{r} & \tau R \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \tag{9}$$

and the physical components of \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{B}^2 are given by

$$\bar{\mathbf{B}} = \bar{\mathbf{F}} \bar{\mathbf{F}}^T = \begin{bmatrix} \eta^2 R'^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{R^2}{r^2} + \tau^2 R^2 & \tau R \\ 0 & \tau R & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{B}}^2 = \begin{bmatrix} \eta^4 R'^4 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \left(\frac{R^2}{r^2} + \tau^2 R^2\right)^2 + \tau^2 R^2 & \tau R \left(\frac{R^2}{r^2} + \tau^2 R^2\right) + \tau R \\ 0 & \tau R \left(\frac{R^2}{r^2} + \tau^2 R^2\right) + \tau R & \tau^2 R^2 + 1 \end{bmatrix} \tag{10}$$

The first three principal strain invariants are

$$I_1 = \eta^2 R'^2 + \frac{R^2}{r^2} + \tau^2 R^2 + 1 \tag{11}$$

$$I_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(1 + \eta^2 R'^2 + \frac{R^2}{r^2} + \tau^2 R^2 \right)^2 - \left(\eta^4 R'^4 + \left(\frac{R^2}{r^2} + \tau^2 R^2 \right)^2 + 2\tau^2 R^2 + 1 \right) \right) \tag{12}$$

$$I_2 = \frac{\eta^2 R^2 R'^2}{r^2} + \frac{R^2}{r^2} + \eta^2 \tau^2 R^2 R'^2 + \eta^2 R'^2 \tag{13}$$

$$I_3 = \frac{\eta^2 R^2 R'^2}{r^2} \tag{14}$$

We obtain the physical components of the Cauchy stress as

$$\bar{\sigma} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{RR} & \sigma_{R\phi} & \sigma_{RZ} \\ \sigma_{\phi R} & \sigma_{\phi\phi} & \sigma_{\phi Z} \\ \sigma_{ZR} & \sigma_{Z\phi} & \sigma_{ZZ} \end{bmatrix} = \omega_0 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \omega_1 \begin{bmatrix} \eta^2 R^{12} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{R^2}{r^2} + \tau^2 R^2 & \tau R \\ 0 & \tau R & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \omega_2 \begin{bmatrix} \eta^4 R^{14} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \left(\frac{R^2}{r^2} + \tau^2 R^2\right)^2 + \tau^2 R^2 & \tau R \left(\frac{R^2}{r^2} + \tau^2 R^2\right) + \tau R \\ 0 & \tau R \left(\frac{R^2}{r^2} + \tau^2 R^2\right) + \tau R & \tau^2 R^2 + 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

We shall consider the Blatz-Ko strain energy function for compressible nonlinear elastic behaviour of the material under study given by Blatz and Ko (1962)

$$W = \frac{\mu}{2} \left(\frac{I_2}{I_3} + 2I_3^{1/2} - 5 \right) \quad (16)$$

Where: μ is the initial shear modulus of the material.

$$\frac{\partial W}{\partial I_2} = \frac{\mu}{2I_3} = \frac{\mu r^2}{2\eta^2 R^2 R^{12}}, \quad \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_3} = \frac{\mu}{2} \left(\frac{r}{\eta R R'} - \frac{r^2}{\eta^2 R^2 R^{12}} - \frac{r^2}{\eta^4 R^2 R^{14}} - \frac{r^4 \tau^2}{\eta^2 R^2 R^{12}} - \frac{r^4}{\eta^2 R^4 R^{12}} \right) \quad (17)$$

$$\omega_0 = 2J \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_3} = \frac{2\eta R R'}{r} \left(\frac{\mu}{2} \left(\frac{r}{\eta R R'} - \frac{r^2}{\eta^2 R^2 R^{12}} - \frac{r^2}{\eta^4 R^2 R^{14}} - \frac{r^4 \tau^2}{\eta^2 R^2 R^{12}} - \frac{r^4}{\eta^2 R^4 R^{12}} \right) \right) \quad (18)$$

$$\omega_0 = 2J \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_3} = \mu \left(1 - \frac{r}{\eta R R'} - \frac{r}{\eta^3 R R^{13}} - \frac{r^3 \tau^2}{\eta R R'} - \frac{r^3}{\eta R^3 R'} \right) \quad (19)$$

$$\omega_1 = 2J^{-1} \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_2} I_1 = \frac{\mu r^3}{\eta R^3 R'} + \frac{\mu r}{\eta^3 R R^{13}} + \frac{\tau^2 \mu r^3}{\eta^3 R R^{13}} + \frac{\mu r^3}{\eta^3 R^3 R^{13}} \quad (20)$$

$$\omega_2 = -2J^{-1} \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_2} = -\frac{\mu r^3}{\eta^3 R^3 R^{13}}. \quad (21)$$

$$\text{Then, } \sigma_{RR} = \mu - \frac{\mu r}{\eta^3 R R^{13}}, \quad \sigma_{\phi\phi} = \mu - \frac{\mu r^3}{\eta R^3 R'} \quad (22)$$

The equilibrium equations in cylindrical coordinates is given as

$$\frac{d\sigma_{RR}}{dr} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{d\sigma_{R\phi}}{d\theta} + \frac{d\sigma_{RZ}}{dz} + \frac{1}{R} (\sigma_{RR} - \sigma_{\phi\phi}) + \rho b_R = \rho a_R \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{d\sigma_{\phi R}}{dr} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{d\sigma_{\phi\phi}}{d\theta} + \frac{d\sigma_{\phi Z}}{dz} + \frac{2}{R} \sigma_{R\phi} + \rho b_{\phi} = \rho a_{\phi} \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{d\sigma_{ZR}}{dr} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{d\sigma_{Z\phi}}{d\theta} + \frac{d\sigma_{ZZ}}{dz} + \frac{1}{R} \sigma_{ZR} + \rho b_Z = \rho a_Z \quad (25)$$

Where b_R, b_{ϕ} and b_Z are the components of the body force

a_R, a_{ϕ} and a_Z are the components of acceleration.

The equilibrium equations in the absence of any body force are reduced to

$$\frac{d\sigma_{RR}}{dr} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{d\sigma_{R\phi}}{d\theta} + \frac{d\sigma_{RZ}}{dz} + \frac{1}{R} (\sigma_{RR} - \sigma_{\phi\phi}) = 0 \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{d\sigma_{\phi R}}{dr} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{d\sigma_{\phi\phi}}{d\theta} + \frac{d\sigma_{\phi Z}}{dz} + \frac{2}{R} \sigma_{R\phi} = 0 \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{d\sigma_{ZR}}{dr} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{d\sigma_{Z\phi}}{d\theta} + \frac{d\sigma_{ZZ}}{dz} + \frac{1}{R} \sigma_{ZR} = 0 \quad (28)$$

We substitute the obtained component stresses into the equilibrium equations above, we get,

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left(\mu - \frac{\mu r}{\eta^3 R R'^3} \right) + \frac{1}{R} \left(-\frac{\mu r}{\eta^3 R R'^3} + \frac{\mu r^3}{\eta R^3 R'} \right) = 0 \quad (29)$$

$$-\left[\frac{\mu R R' - \mu r (3 R R'' + R'^2)}{\eta^3 R^2 R'^4} \right] + \frac{\mu \eta^2 r^3 R'^2 - \mu r R^2}{\eta^3 R^4 R'^3} = 0 \quad (30)$$

Simplifying further,

$$3\mu r R^3 R'' + \mu \eta^2 r^3 R'^3 + \mu r R^2 R'^2 - (\mu R^3 + \mu r R^2) R' = 0 \quad (31)$$

The differential equation obtained above is highly nonlinear and no closed form solution exists hence we will apply numerical method.

Let the quantity dR/dr mathematically describes how the material has been deformed from the reference configuration to the current configuration. Then we can say that

$$\frac{dR}{dr} \Big|_{r=1} = -p \quad (32)$$

where p is the initial pressure applied to the material externally. The negative sign does not necessarily mean the change is negative but rather it means a contraction or decrease in volume.

Equation (32) is physically true since an initially applied pressure will determine the magnitude of the quantity dR/dr . For the purpose of this research we take $p = 0.25 N/m^2$. To this end, we choose our initial condition as $R(1) = 5, R'(1) = -0.25$ (33)

We split the equation (31) into a system of first order ordinary differential equations by letting

$$R'(r) = u(r) \Rightarrow R''(r) = u'(r) \tag{33}$$

We substitute equation (33) into equation (31), we get the system

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{dR}{dr} &= u \\ \frac{du}{dr} &= \frac{(R+r)}{3rR} - \frac{1}{3R}u^2 - \frac{\eta^2 r^2}{3R^2}u^3 \\ R(1) &= 5, \quad u(1) = -0.25 \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{34}$$

We choose the step size $h = 0.1$ for $1 \leq r \leq 2$. Hence. $r_0 = 1, R_0 = 5, \eta = 0.5$ and $u_0 = -0.25$.

Continuity and Convergence Justification

Before applying the fourth-order Runge-Kutta method to the system represented by Equation (34), we verify that the system satisfies the conditions necessary for convergence, particularly the Lipschitz continuity of the nonlinear terms. To demonstrate that $g(r, R, u)$ satisfies the Lipschitz condition in the variables R and u , we see clearly that $\frac{\partial g}{\partial u}, \frac{\partial g}{\partial R}$ is continuous with respect to R and u on any closed and bounded domain where $R > 0, r \in [1, a], a > 1$, and u . Since the partial derivatives are continuous and bounded on this compact domain, Hence, $g(r, R, u)$ is Lipschitz continuous in R and u in the region of interest. Consequently, the system satisfies the conditions of the Picard–Lindelöf theorem, ensuring the existence and uniqueness of the solution and therefore, the application of the fourth-order Runge-Kutta method is justified for this problem.

RESULTS

Wolfram Mathematica version 12 was used to perform a numerical simulation by applying NDSolve with the shooting method to solve the system of differential equations (34). Following Butter, Miller, & Obonin (2024) we analyze the deformation displacement by varying the constant that represents the initial compressibility at different reasonable initial externally applied pressure on the material.

Fig.1: Deformation displacement with $U(1)=-0.01$ and $\eta = 1, 50, 100, 150,$

Fig.2: Deformation displacement with $U(1)=-0.5$ and $\eta = 1, 50, 100, 150,$

Fig.3: Deformation displacement with $U(1)=-0.25$ and $\eta = 1, 50, 100, 150, 200$

Fig.4: Deformation displacement with $U(1)=-0.5$ and $\eta = 1, 50, 100, 150, 200$

Fig.5: Deformation displacement with $U(1) = -0.1$ and $\eta = 1, 50, 100, 150, 200$

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

Fig. 1-5. Represents the deformation displacement $U(r)$ as a function of radius of the cylinder r for different values of initial compressibility η (1, 50, 100, 150, and 200) where the pressure applied to the material externally $u(1) = -0.01, -0.5, -0.25, -0.5, -0.1$ respectively. It was however observed from **Fig. 1** that at $u(1) = -0.01$, the curves gradually shift downward as η increases, demonstrating that materials with larger η are less deformable, however, as it approaches the wall of the cylinder, the displacement is peak as η increases. **Fig. 2.** Shows a similar result as previews but with a slight decrease in the minimum and maximum deformation displacement. **Fig. 3-4.** the curves **initially decrease** before reaching a minimum and then increasing again. This suggests an initial **compression phase** followed by an **expansion phase**; however, it was observed also that as η increases, the deformation displacement reduces, meaning materials with higher η deform less. **Fig. 5.** Shows that as η increases, the deformation displacement curve shifts, showing a trend where higher η values result in smaller deformations at lower values of r but greater deformations at the boundary layers. In general, all curves follow a similar path around the origin, indicating that initial deformation behaviour is nearly identical across different η .

CONCLUSION

The deformation displacement $U(r)$ as a function of the radial distance r within the cylindrical material exhibits distinct trends depending on the initial compressibility η and the externally applied pressure $u(1)$. From the discussion of the plots above, we draw the following conclusions

1. A higher η exhibit less deformation throughout the radial profile, indicating increased material stiffness and resistance to deformation.
2. As η increases, displacement around the origin decreases, but near the boundary layer, deformation tends to peak for higher η .
3. For small negative pressures the displacement is gradual, and materials with higher η show less deformation.
4. For larger negative pressures, the curves initially decrease (compression phase) before increasing (expansion phase).
5. At the origin, all curves behave similarly, indicating that initial deformation response is nearly identical regardless of η .

RECOMMENDATION

1. Engineers and material scientists should consider using materials with higher compressibility parameters (η) when designing components that require flexibility and adaptability under varying loads.
2. For applications where resistance to deformation is crucial, materials with higher η should be preferred to minimize excessive displacement.
3. While numerical simulations provide valuable insights, experimental validation is necessary to confirm theoretical predictions.
4. Future research should explore the effect of different strain energy functions beyond the Blatz-Ko model to validate and extend the findings. Different

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